

Sensibility and Transcendental Illusion: Three Core Tensions

Omer Lipsker,

Tel Aviv University, University of Turin

The Triennial Conference of the Società Italiana di Studi Kantiani

Turin, 27–28 November 2025

The subject of my talk is three core, widely acknowledged tensions in Kant's conception of transcendental illusion. I will suggest that the key to resolving these tensions lies in understanding the role of sensibility in Kant's account of error in his lectures on logic, as the source of psychological causes of error.

Error

1. The FN Thesis: “no force of nature can of itself depart from its own laws” (A294/B350)
 - No cognitive faculty is responsible for error — no faculty originates error-causing representations
2. Error is the property of judgment
3. Error = illusion (major) / set of illusions (minor): subjective representations mistaken for objective ones
 - Transcendental Illusion (TI)
 - Dissertation (1770): assigning sensible epistemological conditions to things in themselves.
 - CpR (1781): TI concerns also the categories and above all **pure reason's supreme principle (SP)**
 - Basic Tension: If error-causing representations originate in our faculties, does this not make the faculties responsible for error, thereby contradicting the FN Thesis?

Let me begin with a few words on Kant's account of error. The thesis from which Kant departs is that “no force of nature departs from its own laws.” We can call it the force-of-nature thesis. This thesis states that no cognitive faculty, as a force of nature, is responsible for error by deviating from its function. We can understand this through the claim that no cognitive faculty—sensibility, understanding, or reason—can originate flawed, that is, error-causing, representations.

The force-of-nature thesis appears in the very first paragraph of the Dialectic and in all the logic lectures, where it is so prevalent that it becomes a kind of mantra. Kant offers several justifications for this thesis. The main idea is that if, for example, we consider the understanding, its laws constitute truth. If these laws could generate error by “deviating,” we would lose the ability to distinguish truth from error and to correct ourselves. The same goes for the other faculties—laws that constitute truth cannot, by themselves, also bring about error. It is also somewhat unintelligible to suppose that a rule could deviate from its own function, as if it could generate its own misapplication.

From this Kant infers that error is a property of judgments, which seems consistent. He also identifies error with illusion, as a case in which subjective representations are mistaken for, or misattributed to, objective ones. In Kant’s logic, error is always explained as an illusion. But here it is worth distinguishing between a major and a minor illusion or error. The former is, according to Kant, a phenomenon that must be analyzed into a set of minor illusions, each of which is an error in itself as a state in which a subjective representation is projected onto an objective one.

You might begin to feel the basic tension that will accompany us in what follows. It becomes more apparent once we place Kant’s account of error against the background of the standard interpretation of transcendental illusion. Kant claims that there are epistemological representations that are subjective because they originate in our faculties and are misattributed to objects as things in themselves. Kant also maintains that this error is necessary. These representations are the forms of intuition and, in the *Critique*, also the categories, as well as the ideas and principles of pure reason, above all pure reason’s supreme principle, which will be our main concern. The question is how our faculties can originate such representations that cause necessary error, without those faculties themselves being responsible for error in a way that would violate the force-of-nature thesis.

Reason as the “Seat” of Transcendental Illusion

- $TI_{(minor)}:SPr \rightarrow SPC$

SPr: Epistemological normative demand for maximum expansion & systematicity (complete explanation)

➤ For any conditioned object, seek the whole series of conditions — seek the unconditioned

SPc: If a conditioned object exists, the whole series of its conditions exists — the unconditioned exists

- Causes

1. Transcendental realism (Willaschek 2018)

2. Moral temptation (Kemp-Smith 2018)

3. **Logical necessity** (Grier 2001)

“it would appear to make no sense to seek the unconditioned unless we also thought that it was there to be found” (Grier 2011, 70)

Let me now zoom in on reason, where the standard story locates the “seat” of transcendental illusion (TI). I will focus on TI^{minor} : the core deception supposed to lie at the basis of the antinomies in particular, and perhaps also the paralogisms and the ideal, as major errors. We shall bear the Antinomies in mind as the main example, because TI^{minor} concerns conditioning relation.

I am simplifying, as there is also a logical maxim in the background. For our purposes, it is enough to think first of reason's regulative supreme principle as an epistemological demand for maximal expansion and inferential systematicity (also understood as complete scientific explanation). Let us also grant Kant that this demand can be translated into a demand to seek the whole series of conditions for a conditioned object, with the series itself, or its first member, then understood as unconditioned, so that the demand is to seek the unconditioned. As a normative demand (a precept) originating in reason, Kant treats it as subjective. This is important if we want to maintain the structure of illusion, in which a subjective representation is mistaken for an objective one.

The illusion (the error) consists in the transition to what Kant calls the constitutive employment of reason. This is the descriptive assertion that if a conditioned object is given or exists, then the whole series, and thus the unconditioned, exists.

I think there are three main causes of this error, which are irreducible to each other:

1. Transcendental realism. According to Kant, if we assume that objects are things in themselves, the transition to the constitutive principle is valid or at least easily

excusable or understandable (I set aside the debate over whether it is valid or merely excusable). Roughly, the idea is that if we understand objects as existing independently of our forms of intuition, as intellectual constructs, we would then have to, or it would make sense to, attribute to them a rational unconditional structure corresponding to our reason. This is the prominent cause of transcendental illusion in the Dialectic (especially in the Antinomies). It is also a legitimate one, because it explains how reason may fall prey to illusion passively, in conformity with the force-of-nature thesis. Reason is not to be blamed; only transcendental realism, which does not originate from reason. Of course, this does not settle the matter; we must then ask why this minor error (what Kant calls a “common prejudice”) is naturally acquired and whether it can be resisted. This interpretation, true as it is, is also too weak on its own, because Kant clearly promotes a narrative in which reason is also accused by itself, independently of transcendental realism.

2. Moral temptation or hope. Kant repeatedly emphasizes a strong temptation connected with the moral worth of the transcendental ideas, and a deep dissatisfaction when the attempt to validate their objects fails. This, I think, is not a secondary element in the emergence of transcendental illusion, but I will set this aside to focus on theoretical reason.
3. Logical necessity. According to Grier’s influential interpretation, the transition to the constitutive principle is logically necessary, as an “application condition” of the supreme regulative principle. Her point is that without assuming that the unconditioned is to be found, it would make no sense to seek it. This brings us to our first tension, as it seems that here necessity and an error-causing function converge in reason.

The Unavoidability and the Psychology Tensions

- The Unavoidability Tension: How can TI be both unavoidable and correctable?

➤ TI is unavoidable and **natural**: 1. necessary (persistent) 2. universal

“This deception is, however, not artificial, but *an entirely natural mistake of common reason*. For through common reason, when something is given as conditioned, we presuppose (in the major premise) the conditions and their series as it were sight unseen, because this is nothing but *the logical requirement of assuming complete premises for a given conclusion*” (A500/B528)

➤ Willascheck's strategy: SPr leads to SPC unavoidably only if one assumes transcendental realism

➤ Grier's strategy: SPC is a necessary assumption for SPr, so only transcendental realism is correctable

- The Psychology Tension: How can pure reason be the bearer of psychological elements?

Our first tension, famously raised by Grier, concerns Kant's repeated claims that TI^{minor} is unavoidable. The claim that TI^{minor} is unavoidable jeopardizes the very project of the *Critique of Pure Reason*, and it is also unintelligible insofar as we cannot understand a law deviating by itself from its function.

Before discussing the two dominant strategies for addressing this tension, let me remind you—as this will be important in what follows—that Kant's slogan in the Dialectic is that TI^{minor} is an unavoidable and natural phenomenon of common or human reason. This means, first, that TI^{minor} is necessary. For Grier, reason cannot think otherwise than by assuming the existence of the unconditioned when applying the supreme regulative principle. In softer readings, necessity implies something that may remain persistent or permanent, or at least still tempting, even after TI^{minor} has been exposed. The second sense is universality; TI^{minor} is something that everyone encounters.

For example, here is a quote from the Antinomies chapter where, just before going on to explain that TI^{minor} is caused by the assumption of transcendental realism, Kant notes that it is also “an entirely natural mistake of common reason.” By the end of this quote, he claims that the illusion occurs due to the logical requirement of assuming complete premises for a given conclusion.

Willaschek's strategy, of blaming transcendental realism for TI, would do justice to the force-of-nature thesis, but not to this quote or to the story of reason as the seat of illusion. As a sole cause, this interpretation is too weak. Taking reason in isolation, it is only able to explain why TI is correctable, not why it is unavoidable.

Grier offers a reading that, in my view, is far too strong. Taking the supreme constitutive principle as necessary for the application of the supreme regulative principle, Grier actually claims that TI^{minor} is not correctable (and should not be correctable, as it has a regulative function). In her view, we can only prevent transcendental realism. So Grier does not really resolve the tension by explaining how the same error, insofar as it originates from reason, is both unavoidable and correctable.

While Willaschek's strategy is too weak with respect to reason, dismissing TI^{minor} as avoidable, and Grier's too strong with respect to reason, treating it as not correctable, I think there is a middle path, which is usually dismissed as it leads to a second tension. We should remember that what Grier frames as a necessary assumption is more often presented by Kant as a kind of need, even desire. On that basis, we should ask how subjective psychological elements can belong to pure reason. This seems to conflict with pure reason's necessity and universality, since psychological elements are empirical. No less perplexing, it seems to conflict with the fact that pure reason is a discursive and not an intuitive faculty.

I think that there is a way to resolve this tension, a way that illuminates the unavoidability tension. The key, which will trigger a third tension, lies in understanding the role of sensibility.

The Sensibility Tension

- [Transcendental Dialectic, First Paragraph](#)

"Hence neither the understanding by itself (without the influence of another cause), nor the senses by themselves, can err [...]. Now because we have no other sources of cognition besides these two, it follows that error is effected only through the unnoticed influence of sensibility on understanding, through which it happens that the subjective grounds of the judgment join with the objective ones, and make the latter deviate from their destination" (A294/B350-1)

➤ [Bennet](#): "this conflicts with everything else Kant says on the subject" (1774, 270)

➤ [Grier](#): This paragraph concerns epistemological conditions

- [The Sensibility Tension](#): Does claiming that sensibility causes error not violate the FN Thesis?

In the first paragraph of the Dialectic, right after the presentation of the force-of-nature thesis, Kant argues that all errors are caused by "the unnoticed influence of sensibility

on the understanding, through which it happens that the subjective grounds of the judgment join with the objective ones.” This is a quote from the logic lectures.

Read against the background of what follows in the Dialectic, Bennett famously claimed that “this [passage] conflicts with everything else Kant says on the subject.” Grier also finds this passage extremely disturbing. She works hard to align these “subjective grounds” with the epistemological conditions of sensibility and understanding. Kant, however, mentions no such condition here. He refers more specifically to “the unnoticed influence of sensibility” on “subjective grounds.” And even by taking Grier’s perspective and treating the forms of intuition as the cause of error, we would still need to explain how this agrees with the force-of-nature thesis stated immediately beforehand. How can sensibility be the cause of error? The answer lies in Kant’s account of error in the logic lectures, which Grier overlooks.

Sensibility in the Lectures on Logic

- Sensibility’s “influence” = psychological forces

Prejudice; imitation; habit; Inclination; laziness; vanity; imagination; wit; inattention; ignorance.

“Logic, since it abstracts from all content, cannot say more of the influence of sensibility than that it presents the subjective ground of our judgment.” (Vienna logic, 24: 825)

“In our sensibility there is something that is related merely to the object, and that is intuition, and something that is related to the subject, and that is *sensation*.” (Vienna logic, 24: 833-4).

- Resolving the Sensibility Tension

1. Sensibility does not cause error through its original representations (forms of intuition). Instead, sensibility acts as the activator or originator of psychological forces.
2. These forces are not inherently flawed, yet they can make the understanding deviate.

In his logic, Kant explicitly connects “the unnoticed influence of sensibility” with psychological subjective forces (*Gemütskräfte*). This is elaborated in the discussion of truth and error and then culminates—referring again to the force-of-nature thesis—in the discussion of prejudice. Here is the list of the main forces. It is, however, not a mere list, for Kant developed quite a sophisticated account. Prejudices, as minor illusions, are the main cause of error. They are produced by three sources working together: prejudices are received through imitation and then, by means of habit, become inclinations that affect our judgments in an unreflective manner. Kant also finds space to discuss his two favorable inclinations, laziness and vanity, and connects prejudices

with imagination, ignorance, and so forth. I maintain that this account deserves to be heard as a psychological explanation of the emergence of errors that functions independently of, yet in correlation with, epistemological diagnosis. I will come back to it in a minute. First, let us ask how this perspective resolves the sensibility tension.

Kant customarily says that “logic, since it abstracts from all content, cannot say more of the influence of sensibility than that it presents the subjective ground of our judgment.” Sometimes he is more specific, claiming that while the objective part of sensibility concerns intuition, the subjective part is sensation. At this level, the cause of error is not any epistemological condition. Sensibility is not to be blamed due to its forms of intuition. It is, first—in correlation with the first quote—merely the neutral medium or representer. Or, on a stronger interpretation that may correlate with the second quote, it is the bearer and even originator of psychological forces. But even according to this strong interpretation, sensibility is not to be blamed, as Kant claims that these forces are not blameworthy; they all have legitimate “natural” roles. Error occurs only when they “influence” the understanding, and they can do so precisely because they originate from a different source, which is why their association with sensibility is crucial.

Now back to Kant’s psychological explanation. It is important to acknowledge, even briefly, the Wolffian background of his assertions. In the first quote, Kant probably refers to thinkers like Baumgarten and Meier, who were intensely engaged with the practice of sensible rules and forces by the common understanding, and with the latter’s place outside logic and within it, as *logica naturalis*. Kant himself, despite claiming that “logic abstracts from all content,” was deeply engaged with his own vision of a logic of the common understanding (or common reason), titled applied logic in the *Critique*. Sensibility’s “psychological forces” may thus function as a code name for an underlying psychological explanation. I do not have the scope to unfold this part of Kant’s logic, which culminates in his account of prejudices, so I will limit myself to three remarks.

Explaining Error

“The consideration of the subjective causes of the use of our understanding and our reason is the explanation of how it comes about that we use our understanding and our reason in this way and not otherwise. Logic shows how we should use them, but not how we actually use them. Logic does not consider whether the understanding is corrupted or not. *The doctrine of prejudices therefore really belongs not to logic but to anthropology. We include it here, however, because it can be very useful for logic instruction.*” (Warschauer, LV2:587-8)

“A general logic, however, is then called applied if it is directed to the rules of the use of the understanding under the *subjective empirical conditions that psychology teaches us*. It therefore has empirical principles, although it is to be *sure general* insofar as it concerns the use of the understanding without regard to the difference of objects.” (A53/B77).

“We have subjective grounds for judgment; they could be better called causes of judgment if we falsely consider these subjective grounds to be objective, so that a *vitium subreptionis* arises. The following can contribute to this: a.) The opinion, predilection [...]. b.) / Custom [...]” (Busolt, 24:640-1)

First, it is worth noting that Kant never omitted his discussion of prejudices from his logic lectures. Moreover, in all four logic lectures from the mid-1780s, Kant says, somewhere towards the end of the discussion, that this detailed account of prejudice, as psychological, does not belong to logic, but that it is still very useful for logical instruction. This is an example of Kant’s ambiguity. He seems to want to purify his logic from psychological elements, but he also understands that, left alone with epistemological diagnosis, we would not be able to explain how errors actually arise.

This carries over into the *Critique*, where Kant leaves room for applied logic, which concerns “the subjective empirical conditions that psychology teaches us.” What I want to emphasize is that, in this passage, Kant argues that although empirical, this logic “is, to be sure, general.” This means that transcendental applied logic’s psychological cause of TI may also be general.

Third, part of the problem is that the traditional error reincarnated in TI^{minor}—subreption—is already expelled from logic and assigned to metaphysics in the Blomberg logic of the early 1770s, and is mentioned only seven times in the logic transcripts. But in the Busolt logic, Kant combines the two levels: in his discussion of prejudices, he identifies “subjective grounds” for subreption, which seem to be epistemological, and then claims that psychological subjective ones can contribute to them. Kant thus appears to affirm a two-layered—epistemological and psychological—analysis of error. It just seems to me more accurate to say, in light of the force-of-nature thesis, that rather than “contributing to error,” the psychological causes cause the

epistemological ones to deviate, so that the latter, and the faculties to which they belong, are not themselves the original causes of error.

Towards a Two-Layered Account

- Diagnosis: epistemological level

SPr: If the unconditioned has a necessary function in the structure of rational thinking the demand to seek it is not an error

- Explanation: psychological level

SPc: What reason “enjoins us to seek is in fact actually there to be found” (Proops 2021, 48)

- **Prejudice** (predilection): excessive trust in reason; Arising from the lust for knowledge
- Produces the Antinomies’ idealizing thesis, the empiricist antithesis, and further dogmatic transformations (e.g., skepticism, logical egoism)
- Scope: Universal (or common) in the history of philosophy and among philosophy students

Willaschek noted that the Dialectic outlines the logical structure of TI but does not explain it. I think this is only partially true, because some explanations are given; for instance, in the section on interests in the Antinomies. In any case, relying on the logic lectures, here is a brief sketch toward a two-layered account of theoretical reason’s role in TI^{minor}.

On the epistemological level, I am not sure that the supreme regulative principle’s demand for expansion and systematicity can be easily translated into a search for the unconditioned. But if this is true, then there is nothing problematic in the latter demand. It is necessary and even central to the structure of pure reason itself, certainly not an error. Kant tries to state this point in describing how reason works naturally by arriving at complete premises or inductively in sciences like mathematics.

The fact that the supreme principle is not flawed (error-producing) is also validated by several regulative functions that flow from it, none of which should be errors. This is the central theme in recent literature, and a very complicated one. Very briefly: there are subjective doctrinal beliefs in the indeterminate existence of the soul and God as noumenal objects (not as objects of nature); the hypothetical employment of the Appendix’s three principles of systematicity without determining their truth value; and even perspectivist readings, to which I am sympathetic, claiming that we do not need to refer to unconditioned objects at all in order to apply coherently the regulative

principle, understood as a mere demand to seek maximal systematicity. These functions do not result in the error aligned with the constitutive principle, because they do not assert that the unconditioned will be found in the course of inquiry. What I want to stress is that these positive strands demonstrate that there is nothing inherently flawed in pure reason's supreme principle. Under certain prescriptions, in relation to some of the ideas, it may even be possible to join with this framework Grier's suggestion of using the fiction that the unconditioned exists for regulative purposes.

The error concerns the thought that the illusion is necessary. In Proops' recent formulation, it is the assertion that what reason "enjoins us to seek is in fact there to be found." This error lies not only in asserting that we will find the unconditioned, but in thinking, like Grier, that this is a necessary requirement. To clarify, I do not deny that we should satisfy our reason if that means applying it coherently, by doctrinal beliefs or something similar, even with reference to the unconditioned. But the thought that we must assume that reason's objects will be found sounds to me like an overestimation and even a misunderstanding of reason's role—thinking that we should satisfy reason instead of taking it to serve our inquiry. This perspective would be more understandable if noumenal objects flowed from pure reason by something like intellectual intuition, and it may be more accepted in mathematics. But it is just a fact that neither in our inquiry into nature, nor in morality, do we have things settled exactly the way reason would have them and yet we are still able to apply reason coherently.

So if in TI^{minor} we take reason too committedly, and even misunderstand its function by thinking that nature should conform to reason, we can ground this in the central prejudice of the logic lectures: the prejudice of excessive trust in reason. This prejudice is not necessary, because it arises from a psychological element, but it is universal—as a predilection or natural inclination. As it is natural, it has a legitimate origin: it stems from the drive for knowledge that makes us attentive to reason. It should also not necessarily be understood as an unlimited trust in reason. It may be enough to be misled if we habitually and justifiably rely on reason's success in other sciences such as mathematics and expect the same to be achievable in metaphysics.

This excessive trust in reason helps Kant explain how dogmatism consolidates in the idealizing version of the Antinomies' thesis, all the way to Schwärmerei, and also the antithesis's empiricism, as well as skepticism, common sense's idealization, and

misology. In Kant’s eyes, these latter negative stances are disappointments and retreats from the initial excessive trust in reason’s abilities. In the logic lectures, this prejudice also serves to explain related issues, for instance logical egoism versus excessive trust in others. Elaborated also in texts such as *Dreams of a Spirit-Seer*, I think Kant tries to deliver an interesting psychological insight concerning the way our excessive trust in reason functions—speaking metaphorically—as a conatus underlying all dogmatic transformations. Kant specifically tries to illustrate that this prejudice is universal, or at least quite common, among philosophy students and in the history of metaphysics.

Conclusions

- Resolving the Sensibility Tension: Sensibility does not cause error through its epistemological representations (forms of intuition). It acts as the activator or originator of psychological forces. These forces are not inherently flawed, yet they can make the understanding deviate.
- Resolving the Psychological Tension: Psychological elements do not belong to the structure of pure reason but are related to it through the natural development of thinking (common reason).
- Resolving the Unavoidability Tension:
 - The SP_r is necessary as part of the structure of pure reason. It is neither correctable nor incorrect, because it is not an error.
 - The SP_c is caused by a natural inclination that is psychologically universal, yet correctable since it does not belong to the structure of pure reason.

To conclude, let me briefly show how the three tensions are resolved.

1. **The Sensibility Tension.** As we saw, sensibility (in its forms of intuition) is not the cause of error at the epistemological level. It is merely the bearer or source of psychological forces, and these forces arise from legitimate functions. Specifically, the cause of the error of excessive trust in reason arises from the drive for knowledge.
2. **The Psychology Tension.** Indeed, psychological elements do not belong to the structure of pure reason, but they are closely related to it through the natural development of thinking (had I more time, I would present here Kant's learning account under the title “common understanding” or “common reason”).
3. **The Unavoidability Tension.** The resolution lies in a two-level structure of Π^{minor} :

The SPr is necessary as part of the structure of pure reason. It is neither correctable nor incorrect, because it is not an error.

The SPc is caused by a natural inclination that, under certain psychological assumptions, is universal or at least quite common, yet correctable since it does not belong to the structure of pure reason.